

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF HIGH-VELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE IN CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This study experimentally and numerically characterizes the high-velocity impact damage in CFRP laminates to clarify the damage extension mechanisms. To this end, we focus on impact damage near perforation. High-velocity impact tests were conducted for two types of cross-ply laminates. At a relatively low velocity less than 200 m/s, a crater with fiber breaks, oblique matrix cracks, and delamination were observed just beneath the impact point. Delamination had a fan shape, which was similar to that observed in low-velocity impact tests. Catastrophic ply-failure zone, which included extensive fiber breaks, matrix cracking, matrix crushing, and delamination, appeared in the middle of the laminate at an impact velocity over 300 m/s. The extension of high-velocity impact damage in composite laminate was then predicted by smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH). A crater was formed by matrix failure and fiber breaks generated in the top 0° ply near the impact point. Ply interfaces were then delaminated, and a matrix cracking and crushing zone appeared in the middle plies. This damage pattern, including the delamination shape, agreed with the observation. Delamination mainly extended at a ply-interface along the matrix crack in the lower ply regardless of the stacking sequence. Based on the experiments and the analyses, the mechanisms of high-velocity impact damage in CFRP laminates will be discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) have been applied to primary load bearing structures in latest airplanes by taking advantage of their high specific strength/stiffness and good fatigue characteristics. In recent years, CFRPs are also used in fan blades and fan cases of turbofan engines. A concern about these composite structures is failure due to high-velocity impact of small stones, birds (bird-strike event), and broken fan-blades (fan-blade out event). Understanding damage extension mechanisms in CFRPs is essential to improve safety against these impact events.

Delamination is easily generated by out-of-plane impact loading in composite laminates. Many studies on low-velocity impact have been published because of severe degradation of compressive strength after impact [1]. A number of studies have been reported on response of CFRPs and generation of debris cloud caused by hyper-velocity impact [2], since shielding is a critical issue in space

applications and in military fields. However, there are few number of studies on impact at a middle velocity range (i.e., near the sound speed in air) despite the importance for aircraft applications.

Conventional studies on high-velocity impact focused mainly on the ballistic limit energy and on energy dissipation during perforation. Cantwell and Morton [3] observed conical shear fracture zone in perforated laminates regardless of the stacking configuration, and proposed a simple perforation model to estimate the influence of target thickness and projectile size on the perforation threshold. The recent advances in experimental studies on high-velocity impacts of composite materials have been summarized in the latest review [4]. Delaminated area has been a topic of interest because delamination is a factor of energy dissipation in high-velocity impact [5-7].

Response of composite plates to high-velocity impact have been analyzed by the finite-element method (FEM) [8-10]. However, impact analysis by the FEM generally requires contact algorithm, remeshing, and handling of greatly-deformed elements. Some numerical analyses of ballistic impact on composite laminates have been presented using the smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH). SPH easily represents contact problems, large deformation and separation, and thus is appropriate to analyze high-velocity impact. Medina and Chen [11] introduced an anisotropic rate-dependent plasticity model, and investigated the influence of the strain rate on damage extension. Shintate and Sekine [12] proposed a particle generation/merger technique and successfully avoided unrealistic numerical fracture in a ballistic impact analysis.

Typical studies on high-velocity impact have focused on characterization of perforation and on the ballistic limit for shielding applications, but there are few detailed discussions on generation and extension of damage in each ply and at each ply-interface. Analyzing the extension of high-velocity impact damage and understanding the mechanisms of damage extension are useful to predict energy absorption and to estimate shielding capability. We thus focus on the high-velocity impact damage near perforation. This study first summarizes high-velocity impact tests on two types of cross-ply laminates, and then predicts damage states by using SPH to discuss the mechanism of damage extension due to high-velocity impact.

2 HIGH-VELOCITY IMPACT TESTS

2.1 Procedure

Carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite laminates (T700S/#2521R, Toray Industries) were used, and the stacking sequence was two types of cross-ply, i.e., $[0_4/90_4]_S$ and $[0/90]_{4S}$. The fiber direction in the top and bottom plies was defined as the 0° direction. The laminates were manufactured by heating and pressing the stacked prepreg sheets in a vacuum chamber. The prepared laminates were cut into square specimens 55 mm on a side and 1.6 mm thick.

Figure 1a depicts a schematic of a high-velocity impact testing machine (Maruwa Electronic Incorporated). This machine consisted of a control unit for the power source, a data logger, and a chamber in which a sphere was shot at the target. The projectile, set in a sabot, was accelerated with high-temperature, high-pressure metal plasma obtained by melting and evaporating an aluminum foil subjected to high-voltage pulse current. The sabot was stopped at the mouth of the gun and only the sphere moved ahead by inertia. The possible velocity range of the projectile was 40 to 1500 m/s. The velocity of the projectile was approximately controlled by the voltage applied to the aluminum foil and was determined by the flight time measured by two acceleration sensors on the mouth of the gun and on the fixture jig. The target specimen was placed in a square-frame jig depicted in Fig. 1b. All four sides of the target were fixed rigidly by the square frame, and a space existed behind the back surface of the target. Bending of the target plate was then possible by the impact loading. The projectile was a steel ball with a diameter of 1.5 mm.

After impact tests, damage states of the front and back surfaces of the target plates were observed by a stereomicroscope. Damage in the cross-section, including the impact point, was observed by an optical microscope. Here, the tested specimens were cut off on a separate line from the impact point not to affect impact-induced damage and were polished by using fine abrasive papers. Delamination was also observed by soft X-ray radiography.

Figure 1: Schematic of the high-velocity impact test.

(a) $[0_4/90_4]_s$ laminate (186 m/s)

(b) $[0/90]_{4s}$ laminate (140 m/s)

Figure 2: Damage state in the cross-section normal to 0° direction.

2.2 Experiment results

A crater was generated on the front surface, and splits extended from its edge. Moreover, fiber breaks and additional short splits appeared inside the crater. This damage pattern on the front surface was independent of the stacking sequence [13]. A single matrix crack was generated on the back surface at a relatively low velocity less than 200 m/s.

Figure 2 depicts the damage states in the cross-section normal to the 0° direction of the cross-ply

laminates at a relatively low velocity less than 200 m/s. The simple $[0_4/90_4]_S$ laminate suffered a crater and accompanying matrix cracks in the top 0° plies, but no damage was observed in the lower plies. In the cross-ply $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminate with many ply interfaces, fiber breaks, matrix cracks and delamination appeared beneath the impact point. Delamination was observed at the interface below transverse plies. This pattern suggested that delamination extended from the crack tips in the upper transverse ply. However, some interfaces in the middle of the thickness were delaminated without matrix cracks in the upper ply, and this damage was caused by interlaminar shear stress.

Figure 3 depicts soft X-ray photographs of these cross-ply laminates. Matrix cracks and fan-shaped delamination were observed near the impact point regardless of the stacking sequence. Delamination extended in both of the 0° and 90° directions.

3 ANALYSIS

3.1 Smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH)

The governing equations for continuum mechanics express the conservation of mass and momentum, and these equations are solved in the updated Lagrangian scheme. The conservation equation of mass is

$$\frac{d\rho}{dt} = -\rho \frac{\partial v^i}{\partial x^i}, \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the density, t is the time, v^i is the velocity, and x^i is the position. The conservation equation of momentum is, at the current configuration,

$$\frac{dv^i}{dt} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \sigma^{ji}}{\partial x^j}, \quad (2)$$

where σ^{ji} is the first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor. Here, the subscripts (superscripts) denote covariant (contravariant) component of a tensor, but there is no difference in these indices, since this study used the Cartesian coordinate system.

A CFRP lamina was considered as an orthotropic elastic material in this analysis. The stress rate $\dot{\sigma}^{ij}$ is calculated from the deformation rate D_{ij} as

$$\dot{\sigma}^{ij} = C_{ijkl} D_{kl}, \quad (3)$$

where C_{ijkl} is the stiffness tensor. The components of the compliance matrix are represented as

$$S_{11} = \frac{1}{E_1}, \quad S_{22} = S_{33} = \frac{1}{E_2}, \quad S_{12} = S_{13} = -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1}, \quad S_{23} = -\frac{\nu_{23}}{E_2}, \quad S_{44} = \frac{1}{G_{23}}, \quad S_{55} = S_{66} = \frac{1}{G_{12}}, \quad (4)$$

where E , G , and ν are the Young's modulus, shear modulus, and Poisson's ratio. Subscripts 1, 2, and 3 denote the fiber direction, the transverse direction, and the through-thickness direction.

Figure 3: Soft X-ray photographs of the impacted targets.

SPH is based on interpolation theory. The method allows a function to be expressed in terms of its values at a set of disordered points using a kernel function. The kernel function W refers to a weighting function and specifies the contribution of a field variable $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ at a certain position \mathbf{x} . The interpolation of $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ is defined as

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \int_D \phi(\mathbf{x}') W(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', h) d\mathbf{x}' . \quad (5)$$

D is the volume considered, and the smoothing length h represents the effective width of the kernel. If there are N particles in the effective width of the kernel function from position \mathbf{x} , the above interpolation is approximated by

$$\langle \phi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \sum_{b=1}^N \phi_b \frac{m_b}{\rho_b} W(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_b, h), \quad (6)$$

where b denotes the label of a neighboring particle, and the brackets $\langle \rangle$ indicate that the variable is approximated by the SPH interpolation. A particle equation for the gradient of $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ can be obtained by using the divergence theorem of Gauss and the fact that the kernel function vanishes at infinity.

$$\langle \nabla \phi(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \int_D \phi(\mathbf{x}') \nabla W(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', h) d\mathbf{x}' = \sum_{b=1}^N \phi_b \frac{m_b}{\rho_b} \nabla W(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_b, h) \quad (7)$$

A cubic B-spline function is used for the kernel function in this study.

The total time derivative (d/dt) is taken in a moving Lagrangian frame, and the governing equations (1) and (2) are transformed into the following set of particle equations:

$$\frac{d\rho_a}{dt} = \rho_a \sum_{b \neq a} \frac{m_b}{\rho_b} \left\{ (v^i)_a - (v^i)_b \right\} \frac{\partial W_{ab}}{\partial x^i}, \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{d(v^j)_a}{dt} = \sum_{b \neq a} m_b \left\{ \frac{(\sigma^{ij})_a}{\rho_a^2} + \frac{(\sigma^{ij})_b}{\rho_b^2} + \delta^{ij} \Pi_{ab} \right\} \frac{\partial W_{ab}}{\partial x^i}, \quad (9)$$

where subscripts a and b denote the labels of the particle of interest and its neighboring particles, Π_{ab} is the artificial viscosity term to stabilize dynamic response and is evaluated between the particles a and b , and δ^{ij} is the unit tensor. The deformation rate tensor and the spin tensor are represented as follows.

$$(D_{ij})_a = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{a \neq b} \frac{m_b}{\rho_b} \left[\left\{ (v_i)_b - (v_i)_a \right\} \frac{\partial W_{ab}}{\partial x^j} + \left\{ (v_j)_b - (v_j)_a \right\} \frac{\partial W_{ab}}{\partial x^i} \right] \quad (10)$$

$$(W_{ij})_a = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{a \neq b} \frac{m_b}{\rho_b} \left[\left\{ (v_i)_b - (v_i)_a \right\} \frac{\partial W_{ab}}{\partial x^j} - \left\{ (v_j)_b - (v_j)_a \right\} \frac{\partial W_{ab}}{\partial x^i} \right] \quad (11)$$

The time-step size should be sufficiently small to stably analyze the time integration. Time step Δt is determined by the Courant-Friedrichs-Levy condition.

3.2 Analytical model

The analytical model is illustrated in Fig. 4. A quarter of the whole system was modeled considering the symmetry, and the CFRP target was 6.0 mm long, 6.0 mm wide, and 1.6 mm thick; the diameter of the projectile was 1.5 mm. The initial spacing between neighboring particles was 0.05 mm, and there were 464382 particles. Each particle was recognized as 0° ply or 90° ply according to the stacking sequence of $[0_4/90_4]_S$ and $[0/90]_{4S}$, and the relevant material properties were assigned. There were 32 particles in the through-thickness (z) direction of the target, and a single ply of the $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminate was consisted of two particles in the z -direction. The laminate was not fixed, and the projectile collided vertically with the laminate at an initial velocity of 200 m/s. The authors [14] presented high-velocity impact analysis, in which interlayer particles were inserted in the target plate to represent delamination. However, this study removed these interlayer particles not to affect the stiffness especially in $[0/90]_{4S}$ lamination.

Figure 4: Quarter SPH model considering the symmetry.

This analysis applied Chang-Chang failure criteria with a delamination criterion [15] to the CFRP laminate to identify the damage mode in each particle. The following equations are evaluated at every time integration step. Hereafter, stress components are expressed in the coordinate system of an orthotropic material, i.e., the subscript 1 is the fiber longitudinal direction. Fiber failure is detected by the following condition.

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{F_L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{F_{LTf}^2}\right) \geq 1 \quad (14)$$

Here, F denotes the strength, subscripts L and T represent the fiber longitudinal direction and the transverse direction, and the following lower-case subscripts represent the fracture mode of tension (t), compression (c), and shear (s). Longitudinal tensile strength F_{Lt} (compressive strength F_{Lc}) is applied to the term F_L when $\sigma_{11} \geq 0$ ($\sigma_{11} < 0$). F_{LTf} is the shear strength involving fiber failure. Matrix cracking is determined by the following condition in the case $\sigma_{22} \geq 0$.

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{F_{Tt}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{F_{LTs}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{F_{TTs}}\right)^2 \geq 1, \text{ if } \sigma_{22} \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

When $\sigma_{22} < 0$, instead Eq. (15), matrix crushing is determined.

$$\frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{-\sigma_{22}}{F_{LTs}}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{4} \frac{F_{Tc}^2 \sigma_{22}}{F_{LTs}^2 F_{Tc}} - \frac{\sigma_{22}}{F_{Tc}} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{F_{LTs}}\right)^2 \geq 1, \text{ if } \sigma_{22} < 0 \quad (16)$$

Delamination is detected by

$$\left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle}{F_{Tt}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{F_{TTs}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{31}}{F_{LTs}}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (17)$$

where $\langle \rangle$ is the Macaulay brackets, and the first term of the left-hand side is removed if $\sigma_{33} < 0$. Equation (17) is evaluated at the particles next to the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ ply interface.

If a particle was assumed to break, the stiffness and stresses in the particle were degraded, considering the stiffness reduction due to the damage and the mechanism of stress transfer. When one of the failure criteria was satisfied, the stress components related to the damage mode were set to zero, and the relevant stiffness was updated to the degraded value. The degradation factors should be zero at a crack surface, but nonzero values were applied considering stress recovery in a particle. In order to transfer compressive stresses, all broken particles were not removed, and slightly large degradation factors were used in the compression failure modes.

4 ANALYTICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5 depicts extension of damage beneath the impact point in the cross-section of $[0_4/90_4]_S$ laminate. Matrix damage in the upper 0° ply reached the upper ply-interface at $1 \mu s$ after contact, and delamination was then generated near the crack tip. Extensive fiber breaks, matrix cracking and crushing formed a crater until $2 \mu s$. A single matrix crack was generated in the lower 0° ply after $2 \mu s$, which agreed well with the observation of the back surface and the soft X-ray photograph (Fig. 3a). In the cross-section normal to the 0° direction, no fiber break was predicted in the 90° ply (longitudinal ply) and delamination at the lower interface was small. This damage pattern agreed well with the observation (Fig. 2a). Delamination at the lower interface extended in the 0° direction concurrently with the single matrix crack in the lower 0° ply. This result indicated that the matrix crack in the lower ply induced the delamination.

Figure 6 depicts the damage at the ply-interfaces of the $[0_4/90_4]_S$ laminate. Rectangular delamination was generated at the upper interface due to indentation of the projectile. Peanut-shaped delamination appeared along the matrix crack at the lower interface, which coincided with that observed in the low-velocity impact. Figure 6c is the projection view of the delamination at the two interfaces. The obtained damage pattern agreed well with the soft X-ray photograph (Fig. 3a).

Figure 5: Damage extension in the simple cross-ply $[0_4/90_4]_S$ laminate.

Figure 6: Damage at the ply-interface of the simple cross-ply $[0_4/90_4]_s$ laminate.

Figure 7 depicts extension of damage in the cross-section of the $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminate. The predicted damaged area was larger than that in the microphotograph of the cross-section (Fig. 2b). Handling of the particles satisfying the criterion of delamination onset caused this discrepancy. The ratio of particles (thickness) possible to be delaminated to the total particles (thickness) was 44%, and the influence of the stiffness reduction in the delaminated particles could not be negligible. Furthermore, when a particle was determined to be delaminated, stresses in the particle were set to zero, and surrounding particles have to carry the stress drop. This trend will be improved by using finer particles that simulate the infinitesimal thickness of a ply-interface, although calculating cost will increase.

Most plies near the front surface were damaged in the cross-sections. This large damaged area would be caused by handling of the delaminated particles. Although many ply-interfaces were damaged, delamination extended below a transverse ply especially near the back surface, and this trend agreed with the observation of the cross-section (Fig. 2b). Moreover, predicted delamination area increased with approaching the back surface, and this result confirmed the description that delamination was generated from the tip of a crack in the upper ply.

Figure 8 presents the projection view of the damage at the ply-interfaces of the cross-ply $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminate. The projected damage exhibited a circular shape, which agreed well with the soft X-ray photograph (Fig. 3b). Although the damage was overestimated, the projected delamination area of $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminate was smaller than that of the simple $[0_4/90_4]_s$ laminate. The $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminate had more number of interfaces than the $[0_4/90_4]_s$ laminate. The kinetic energy of the projectile was then absorbed by many interface cracking, even if delaminated area at each interface was small.

Based on the above experiments and analyses, the mechanism of damage extension due to high-velocity impact is estimated as follows. In general, damage extends from the top ply to the bottom ply due to the propagation of stress wave. (1) A crater is formed on the front surface by extensive fiber breaks and matrix damage. The fiber breaks are caused mainly by shear stress. (2) When matrix damage reaches the first ply-interface, delamination is generated near the crack tip. (3) Matrix cracking and crushing, as well as fiber breaks, grow in the inner ply. (4) The second interface is delaminated along the matrix crack in the lower ply. Fan-shaped or peanut-shaped delamination is formed just like the delamination observed in the low-velocity impact. (5) Local bending deformation causes the matrix crack in the bottom ply, which is observed as the crack on the back surface.

Delamination is generated from the crack tip in the upper neighboring ply along the crack in the lower neighboring ply. The delaminated area of the lower interface is usually larger than that of the upper interface. Delamination is a major factor of energy dissipation; the other factor is, of course, fiber breaks. Therefore, a stacking sequence that includes more ply-interfaces has ability to absorb greater energy. Although simple discussion is difficult, moderately good interfacial properties will help prevent perforation, since interfaces have to be delaminated to absorb the kinetic energy.

(a) Cross-section normal to the 0° direction

(b) Cross-section parallel to the 0° direction

Figure 7: Damage extension in the cross-ply $[0/90]_{4s}$ laminate with many ply-interfaces.

Figure 8: Projection view of the damage at the ply-interfaces of the cross-ply $[0/90]_{4s}$ laminate.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study performed high-velocity impact tests for two types of cross-ply laminates. Extension of the high-velocity impact damage was analyzed by smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH). The predicted damage patterns of the two laminates agreed well with the observations in the experiment. The major damage in the high-velocity impact events is the catastrophic ply-failure (including the crater) and delamination. Matrix damage and delamination extended sequentially from the top ply to the bottom ply due to the propagation of stress wave. At the relatively low velocity less than 200 m/s, inner ply-failure zone did not appear, and delamination was generated from the crack tip in the upper neighboring ply along the crack in the lower neighboring ply. This damage pattern was independent of the stacking sequence. Comparison of the damage between the two cross-ply laminates suggested that a stacking sequence that includes more ply-interfaces had ability to absorb greater energy.

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